

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B417
 Date: 09 Nov 2008
 Take Off: 09:58:34
 Landing: 15:23:41
 Flight Time 5h 25m 07s

Campaign: VOCALS – 20 degrees South Flight 5

Operating Area: S.E. Pacific Ocean off the coast of northern Chile

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Luc Lathouwers	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Alan Roberts	Directflight	
3	CCM1	Dawn Quinn	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist 1	Grant Allen	Manchester University	
5	Mission Scientist 2	Steve Abel	Met Office	
6	Flight Manager	Jim Crawford	FAAM	
7	Core Chem	Doug Anderson	FAAM	
8	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office	
9	SWS / SHIMS	Debbie O'Sullivan	Met Office	
10	ARIES	Stuart Rogers	Met Office	
11	CAPS / 2DS	Huge Coe	Manchester University	
12	AMS	Paul Williams	Manchester University	
13	Wet Neph / PSAP / Filters	James Bowles	Met Office	
14	VACC	Mark Bart	Leeds University	
15	CVI	Paul Barrett	Met Office	
16	MARSS	Jeff Norwood-Brown	Met Office	
17	CCN	unmanned	-	
18				
19				

Flight Track:

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B417

Date: 09 November 2008

Project: VOCALS

Location: Pacific off coast of northern Chile

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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093404		gin	0.10 kft	000	off on its own journey after switched on - reset
095419		ASP	0.10 kft	006	open
095436		gin	0.10 kft	006	restarted
095834		T/O	0.07 kft	006	Arica
095834	100438	Profile 1	0.36 - 6.0 kft	006	start at t/o
100439	101050	Run 1	6.0 kft	006	
100701		nev	6.0 kft	223	zero
100834		JW	6.0 kft	224	zero
101051	101746	Profile 2	6.0 - 0.00 kft	224	50ft
101352		cloud	3.2 kft	224	top 3600ft
101746	101818	Profile 3	0.00 - 0.34 kft	223	50ft
101818	102827	Run 2.1	0.41 - 0.45 kft	223	
101938		r2.1	0.36 kft	223	500ft
102742		heimann	0.42 kft	223	cal 10 qnh 1016
102827	102858	Profile 4	0.45 - 0.91 kft	222	
102859	103408	Run 2.2	0.91 - 0.92 kft	219	
102921		r 2.2	0.94 kft	216	1000ft
102950		nev	0.95 kft	217	zero
103036		JW	0.93 kft	223	zero
103408	103726	Profile 5	0.92 - 3.7 kft	221	
103635		!	3.1 kft	226	point A
103726	104729	Run 2.3	3.7 - 3.8 kft	269	
103806		r2.3	3.7 kft	267	3700ft
103845		!	3.6 kft	268	qnh 1016
104226		!	3.8 kft	270	3700->3900 to remain in cloud
104729	104917	Profile 6	3.8 - 5.2 kft	269	
104917	105629	Profile 7	5.2 - -.05 kft	268	50ft
105639	110658	Run 3.1	0.01 - 0.02 kft	266	
105717		r3.1	0.02 kft	267	100ft
110536		!	0.02 kft	266	port aft dlu reset
110658	110949	Profile 8	0.02 - 2.8 kft	269	
110722		heimann	0.43 kft	267	cal10
110950	111958	Run 3.2	2.8 - 2.4 kft	270	
111031		r3.2	2.5 kft	271	->2500ft to stay clear of cloud
111104		!	2.4 kft	266	qnh 1018
111958	112107	Profile 9	2.4 - 3.4 kft	267	
112108	113248	Run 3.3	3.4 kft	268	
112708		heimann	3.4 kft	269	cal06
113249	113522	Profile 10	3.4 - 5.6 kft	266	cloud tops fl044 / 4700ft
113522	114211	Profile 11	5.6 - -.09 kft	268	50ft
114211	114447	Profile 12	-.09 - 2.3 kft	267	50ft
114447	115608	Run 4.1	2.3 kft	268	
114517		r4.1	2.3 kft	268	2500ft
115608	115713	Profile 13	2.3 - 3.3 kft	268	
115714	120727	Run 4.2	3.3 - 3.7 kft	264	
115804		r4.2	3.4 kft	266	3700ft
115816		!	3.5 kft	267	qnh 1019
120727	120911	Profile 14	3.7 - 5.4 kft	267	
120830		!	4.8 kft	267	cloud top 4600
120911	121615	Profile 15	5.4 - -.11 kft	265	50ft
121219		!	2.7 kft	266	cloud base 3000ft
121625	122644	Run 5.1	-.06 kft	267	
121712		r5.1	-.05 kft	269	100ft
122023		!	-.06 kft	268	point Bravo
122645	122915	Profile 16	-.03 - 2.3 kft	269	
122915	123842	Run 5.2	2.3 kft	265	
122945		r5.2	2.3 kft	268	2500ft
123252		!	2.3 kft	357	turn onto reciprocal

79 51W

123843	124038	Profile 17	2.3 - 4.0 kft	099	
124038	125039	Run 5.3	4.0 kft	099	
124117		r5.3	4.0 kft	098	4200ft
125039	125641	Profile 18	4.0 - 9.8 kft	095	
125642	130307	Profile 19	9.8 - 4.6 kft	092	
130152		heimann	5.4 kft	093	cal06
130308	131309	Run 6.1	4.6 - 4.5 kft	093	
130341		r6.1	4.6 kft	096	4700ft
131309	131350	Profile 20	4.5 - 4.0 kft	093	
131350	132350	Run 6.2	4.0 kft	096	
131421		r6.2	4.0 kft	096	4200ft
131448		heimann	4.0 kft	094	cal 10
132351	132540	Profile 21	4.0 - 2.3 kft	093	
132541	133553	Run 6.3	2.3 kft	093	
133553	133922	Profile 22	2.3 - -.10 kft	094	50ft
133922	134602	Profile 23	-.10 - 5.8 kft	093	50ft 6000
134603	134730	Profile 24	5.7 - 4.4 kft	094	6000
134731	135734	Run 7.1	4.4 kft	094	
134808		r7.1	4.4 kft	093	4600ft
135734	135800	Profile 25	4.4 - 4.0 kft	089	
135800	140802	Run 7.2	4.0 - 3.8 kft	089	
135813		r7.2	4.0 kft	090	4200ft
135843		r7.2	3.9 kft	093	4000ft
135904		!	3.8 kft	094	qnh 1021
140802	140911	Profile 26	3.8 - 2.7 kft	091	
140911	141912	Run 7.3	2.7 kft	090	
140954		r7.3	2.7 kft	092	2900ft
141016		!	2.7 kft	093	qnh 1021
141043		!	2.7 kft	093	cloud base 3250ft
141912	142303	Profile 27	2.7 - -.07 kft	092	50ft
142304	142922	Profile 28	-.07 - 5.9 kft	093	50ft 6000ft
142648		!	3.5 kft	093	cloud base fl033
142700		heimann	3.7 kft	094	cal 10
142729		!	4.1 kft	090	cloud tops fl039
142922	143206	Profile 29	5.9 - 3.4 kft	091	6000ft
143136		!			point Alpha
143206	144235	Run 8.1	3.4 - 3.8 kft	089	
143234		!	3.7 kft	092	3900ft
143646		!	3.7 kft	089	Dornier overpass (ish)
144235	144300	Profile 30	3.8 - 3.9 kft	046	point alpha +30secs
144300	144822	Run 8.2	3.9 - 3.8 kft	048	
144822	144922	Profile 31	3.8 - 2.8 kft	047	

following added from written logs as flight manager fltsumm locked up

144922	145949	Run 8.3	2900ft
145949	150252	Profile 32	to 50ft
150252	150752	profile 33	to 5000ft
152341			land Arica

DRS kept running after landing for intercomparison foe about 1 hr

B417 Track 09-NOV-08

SCAR -> SCDA - Overview

NavData Cycle 2008-11 Expires: Thursday, 20 November 2008.

Scale: 1:3410780 (1 inch = 46.78 naut mi). Printed on 07 Nov 2008

7 6 9 9 6 ; 6 8

FliteStar 9.4.2.0

FAAM Sortie, Flight B417
VOCALS 20°S Cross-section #5
Sun 9th November 2008

T/O - 0700 local (1000 UTC)
Landing ~1145 local (1445 UTC)

Mission Scientists: Grant Allen, Steve Abel

Operating Area: SE Pacific Ocean, off west coast of northern Chile, along lat line 20S

Waypoints: ALPHA: 72°W 20°S
BRAVO: 79°W 20°S

Sortie Objectives: To sample aerosol and Sc cloud as a function of distance from the coast to the pristine background (at times operating simultaneously with the Dornier 228 which will be remote sensing from FL150 - along same latitude)

Weather: High pressure system off shore capping a marine boundary layer with widespread Sc cloud. Southerly mean flow. Coastal cell defining a coastal “bite” in cloud character offshore.

Information:

Latest Sat image to be inserted prior to take-off

Key Instrument Details:

SWS – as per instructions.

ARIES – as per instructions

CVI - During high level operate in aerosol mode with CVI hygrometer operating.

CVI – during in cloud runs operate in counterflow mode: **AMS** to sample from it

Wet Neph – operated during all of 500ft runs

AMS, SMPS, – to operate from Rosemount inlets during aerosol and high level runs and profiles; to operate on CVI during in-cloud runs.

Filters – to be exposed on below cloud runs at discretion of mission Scientist(s). The sample tube should be blown through before first filter cartridges deployed

FAAM Sortie, Flight B417 - VOCALS 20°S Cross-section #5

Detailed Flight schedule:

1. Take off and profile ascent 1000 ft/min immediately to 6,000 ft amsl to check instrumentation
[10 min; T=0h 10 min]
2. Continue towards ALPHA, beginning cycle below starting with immediate profile descent to 50ft.
[0 min; T=0h 10 min]
3. Perform cycle consisting of a-f below
 - a. profile descent to 50ft amsl,
 - b. profile climb to 500ft amsl and carry out 10 min straight/level run (SLR)
 - c. * On first cycle only profile climb to 1500ft and carry out 3min SLR for CVI flow validation
 - d. Profile climb to 500ft below cloud-base (CB) and carry out 10-min SLR run
 - e. climb to 500ft below cloud top (CT) and carry out 10-min SLR run,
 - f. Profile ascent to 1000ft above CT.
4. At point ALPHA turn onto westerly heading and continue profile cycle as described above.
[15 min; T=0h 25 min]
5. Repeat item 3 until arrival at point BRAVO.
[2 h; T=2h 25m]
6. At point BRAVO, turn 180 degrees onto reciprocal path toward ALPHA and perform profile ascent in the turn to FL100 followed by immediate profile descent to 50ft amsl, resuming cycles of straight/level cycle as per item 3
[20 m; T=2h55m]
7. Continue from point ALPHA and recover to Arica, repeating cycle as item 3, as far as possible until approach into Arica and land
[1h 55m; T=4h 50m]

BAE-146 Scientist Mission Summary Report (VOCALS)

Author of report: Grant Allen

Mission Number: B417

Type of Mission: 20-South

Start of Mission(UTC): 2008/11/09 09:30

End of Mission(UTC): 2008/11/09 15:10

Submitted at(UTC): 2008/11/13 22:42

MISSION REPORT:

This was a standard 20-degree South cross-section mission going through point ALPHA, with a take-off at 06:30 local time. The flight was not coordinated with other aircraft except for the Dornier-228, which included a simple overpass of the Dornier during its westward leg. A full intercomparison was not possible due to delayed take-off by the Dornier due to an engine fault on the apron.

Flight Pattern:

1. Take off and profile ascent 1000 ft/min immediately to 6000 ft amsl to check instrumentation. Cloud tops near the coast were noted to be 3600 ft.
2. Descent to 500ft for a 10-minute SLR. Cloud was noted to thicken as we flew out from the coast. Detached Cu was noted below the main Sc deck.
3. Ascent to 1000 ft for SLR 10-min run. No significant pollution of aerosol gradient or levels were noted.
4. Ascent to 3700 ft for in-cloud run for 10 mins. Cloud was thin. FSSP reported 3500/cc with a diameter of 10 um. Slight climb over tun to stay in cloud to 3900 ft due to thin nature of cloud.
5. Sawtooth up to 6000 ft and down to 50 ft. Cloud tops were noted to be 4300 ft and base at 3500 ft. AMS reported 1.5 ug m⁻³ SO₄ at low level.
6. SLR at 2500 ft for 10 min run below cloud. No change in aerosol

7. Climb to 3500 ft for in cloud run 10 mins. Higher drizzle and cloud particle concs than previous run.
8. Sawtooth to 6000 ft followed by descent to 50 ft. Slight pollution layer was noted on the climb at 5000 ft. CO up to 85 ppbv, O3 up to 40 ppbv (twice the MBL background).
9. Climb to 2500 ft for 10 min SLR. Slightly cleaner than previously with AMS reporting 1.3 ug m⁻³.
10. Climb to 3700 ft for 10 min in cloud. CB was 3200 ft. Increased drizzle noted with increased mean volume diameters relative to previous runs.
11. Saw tooth to 6000 ft and descent to 50 ft. Pollution layer again noted above cloud coincident with wind sheer above MBL associated with a change in advected airmass.
12. 10 min SLR at 2500 ft. And turn at western point (79 deg 51') to return home.
13. Climb to 4200 ft for SLR in cloud. LWC was 0.6, 450/cc, 20 um diameters
14. Climb to 4750 ft for turbulence measurements. Maxima were around 1.5 ms⁻¹.
15. The same profile cycle was repeated on the return to Arica. Cloud bases were noted to be around 3200 ft on the return with lower CTH at 4000 ft on return.
16. The Dornier was overhead at 15000 ft at 14:34 UTC while we were at 3890 ft going in westward direction.
17. A thinning in cloud was noted within 100 NM of the coast, with a thickening over the coast itself.

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comments : gstoss at ucar.edu

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. ⁴¹⁷..... Date 9/11/08..... Name F. ALLEN..... Page 1 of 4.....

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
09:30	/	0		Arica	Surface conditions: Cloudy Sc 8/8, Sat picture shows cloud all around area of ops. P=1015 mb.
10:00					Take-off en route to Alpha. Plat take-off to 6000ft.
	R1				cloud top 3700 ft on P1.
10:10:51	P2↓	↓500ft		227°	CTH = 3600ft.
	P3↑	500ft			
10:18:18	R2-1	500ft	220°	225°	500ft SLR 10-min Cloud thickening out to sea.
10:28	P4↑	1000ft	220°		Cloud base not much higher than w/ lots of detached Cu below Sc deck.
10:34	P5↑		224°		In-cloud 10-min SLR.
10:38	R2.3	3700ft	220°		Thin cloud. FSSP 350/α. 10µm CDR-180 10µm: Dried > 100µm 2. 350-cms.
10:42	/	↑3700ft			10-11µm - flight climb to stay in cloud.
10:48	P6↑				Cloud tops at 4300ft.
10:52	P7↓	Down Soft.			Cloud base at 3500ft.
10:56	3-1	100ft			1.5 µg m ⁻³ SO ₄ , 120, 56ts
11:07	P8↑	250ft			10-min SLR below cloud.
11:10	R3-2	2500ft			10-min SLR SO ₄ = 1.5 µg m ⁻³ .
11:21	3-3	3500ft			In-cloud run -

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B.....⁴⁷ Date9/11/08 Name G. ALLEN Page2 of4

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
11:22					cloud physics - CDP - 80/mm, dia = 20-21µm. FSSP = 100, 20µm CDP = 40/1km. ~ 700µm. CAS = 20µm. WWC = 0.5. 230-240/cu. Dia =
11:28					Increasing dia. through run. 20-c - 80/1km. drizzle. 200µm sizes. 80/1km
11:32	P10↑	5700ft	267°		4700ft - CTH. Slight pollution layer above cloud at 5000ft. CO > 85ppbv. O ₃ > 40ppbv. No aerosol or nest trace.
11:42	P11↑	60ft			50ft → 250ft
11:45	R4-1	2500ft	268°		Sub-cloud run 1.3µg Sol ₄ .
11:57	R4-2	3700ft	266°		3200ft - cloud base. CDP - 125/cc, dia = 18µm. FSSP = 200/cc. (17µm) drizzle: 40/1h. 250µm. CAS = 300/cu. 0.32 WWC.
12:07	P14↑	5800ft			Sub-totl. CTH = 4600ft.
12:09	P15↓	~50ft			80 CO ppbv, 32 ppbv O ₃ above cloud - cloud base ~ 2800ft. CO. 68 ppbv : O ₃ = 22 ppbv
12:20					Passing original Bravo.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. 417 Date 9/11/08 Name G. ALLEN Page 3 of 4

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
12:26	R52	2500ft			Sub-cloud run for 10-min - On turn super sat changed to 0-4 79° 51' W - further west point
12:39	R17	4700ft			10 min - SLR in cloud.
12:41	R53	4200ft			0.6 LWC. 450/cc. 20µm (12:44) 20µm 300µm 10
12:50	P18	↑ 1000ft			
13:03	P19	↓ 1000ft			4750ft - Turbulence (0.5 → 1.5 m/s)
13:13	P20	↓ 4200ft			4200ft - In-cloud run. 10 min
13:17					CDP - 130/cc. dia = 21µm 70/Water. FSSP = 120/cc. diam = 19/20µm - 250µm 0.5 LWC. 420/cc. Hottest 0.4 LWC.
13:20				76.97° W.	to 4510:45 local 11:35 local 70 min budget
13:31	R61				1.1 µg/m ³ 50µm. 2500ccw: 130 - 40/75 alt 0.1.
13:38	P26	↓ 500ft			Down to 500ft then up to 6000ft.
13:46	P24	↓ 4500			
13:47:20	R7.1	4500ft			Cloud tops. 2(0.5 → 1 m/s) -
13:58:10	R7.2	6000ft			In-cloud run dropped 200ft.
14:00		4000ft			CDP - 100/cc. Dia = 20µm FSSP = 150/cc. 21µm. 30% Drizzle - CAS.
14:08	P26 b	2000ft			CB = 3250ft.
14:15	R7.3	2900ft			VMSR - AMS 11 µg m ⁻³ .
14:19	P27	↓ 500ft			

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. 417 Date 9/11/08 Name GALLEN Page 4 of 4

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
14:19	P27	↓ 500ft	90°	73.3°W	Dornier had delayed take-off due to engine problem. Took off at 10:39 local. RV mlw at 11:35 on local at
					We have coordinated at in-cloud for run.
14:23	P28	↑ 6000ft	90°	73.1°W	12hls, 145°.
					CTH at 4000ft.
14:29	P29b	3900ft	90°	72°55'W	To 3500ft for *Dornier comparison at 14:34.
					cloud is very thin. CB at 3600ft. Tops at 4000ft.
					CDP - 150, Dia 10µm. FSSP 200-3m/sec
					Dia 10µm. Orizole 5µm.
14:36:50					Dornier pass at 3890ft
14:45	3100ft				10-min sea cloud tops.
14:49	2400ft	2900ft	90°	71°31'W, 71°31'W	Sub-cloud aerosol run.
14:57					Detached cu below main Sc deck close to coast.
15:05					Descent to 50ft and up to 500ft for end of science at 15:10.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B.417... Date 9.11.11.05..... Name STEVE AREL..... Page 1.... of 6....

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
095834	T10				Initial profile to 6000' to check instruments. QW data not correct → reset at 6000'
101051	P2↓	6000' → 50'			Large gap in SC. Had some on initial profile after T10 Cloud top ~ 3600' → estimate from FFD forward camera. Neph area increased to ~12m ² in BL * sat pic shows clearance in SC near coast. Some T and Td structure in BL from ~ 950mbar. Few small T inversions.
101766	P3↑	50' - 500'			
101938	R2-1	500'			O ₃ ~ 15m ⁻¹ CO ~ 65ppb
10230					Can see small patchy Cu below SC deck to out of window.
	P4↑	500' → 1000'			
102858	R2-2	1000'			CVI flow rate set.
103408	P5↑				Profile into cloud. Couple of small T inversions at 930-940mbar.
103806	R2-3	3800'			Very thin cloud layer - few 100' thick. LWC ~ 0.28 gm ⁻³ FSSP ~ 350 cc ⁻¹ MWD 19µm COP ~ 180 cc ⁻¹ MWD 19µm EX - some 10µm drizzle drops

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B...417... Date 9/11/05... Name STEVE AREL... Page 2... of 6...

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					w ~ ±1ms ⁻¹ along this run.
104052					3ms ⁻¹ peak ~ at cloud base.
104200					Gently increase altitude to 3900'
					LWC ~ 0.1gm ⁻³
104917	P7↓				Profile from above cloud to 50'
					Nice triangular profile in LWC
					peak ~ 0.35gm ⁻³ . BL looks
					more well mixed than near
					coast → none of the Turbidity
					at 930-940mbar that we saw before
105639	R3-1	100'			Sulphate ~ 1.5µgm ⁻³
					Sea surface flat ^{quite} flat → no
					white capping. VACC not seems
					much sea salt. C _{sea} ~ 10µm ⁻¹
					CO ~ 66ppb. SW cloud fully covered clouds
110658	P8↑				
110950	R3-2	2500'			Some drizzle below cloud ~ 20s
					SW seeing more variability in cloud
					above cv. 2D-C only small
					drizzle rates along this run.
					Typical w ~ ±1ms ⁻¹ . Occasionally
					up to ±2ms ⁻¹ . Higher drizzle concs
					towards end of run
111958	P9↑				profile into cloud.
112108	R3-3	3500'			In cloud run LWC 0.1-0.2gm ⁻³

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B.1417.. Date 9/11/05..... Name STEVE ABEL..... Page 3 of 6

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					CDPN-80cc ⁻¹ MWD ~ 20µm
					FJIP N - 100cc ⁻¹ MWD ~ 20µm
					20-C ~ 40L ⁻¹ drizzle drops up to ~ 70µm.
					CAS ~ 250cc ⁻¹ MWD ~ 20µm
					LWC increasing along run. to ~ 0.4gm ⁻³ at 112419
112749					Drizzle up to ~ 50L ⁻¹ ~ 200µm drops Good agreement between JW and NTCW along this run. NLWC ~ 0.1gm ⁻³ lower
113249	PWA				Cloud top 6700' LWC at cloud top ~ 0.6gm ⁻³ Elevated CO and O ₃ above cloud. Neph size didn't increase → aged aerosol with little aerosol?
113522	P11↓	above cloud to 50'			Nice classic triangular LWC profile in S. ^{peak ~ 0.75gm⁻³} Cloud base 2900' Surface wind ~ 47 from previous descent to 50' → more white capping BL well mixed.
114467	Rk-1	2500'			Run below cloud base. - Very low drizzle rates. v ~ ± 1ms ⁻¹ with occasional odd peak to 2ms ⁻¹

Mission Scientist's Log

121200 ¹²⁰⁸⁰⁰
121440

Flight No B.4.7 Date 9/11/2008 Name STEVE ABEL Page 4 of 6

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
115516					Cloud base looks to be dropping quite a bit. Co-incident with drizzle increasing
115608	P13↑	ascend into cloud			Cloud base 3200' with patches below this. COP ~ 125cc ⁻¹ MWD ~ 18µm
120819	P14-2	in cloud run			FSSP ~ 200cc ⁻¹ MWD ~ 17µm 20C variable to about 10C ~ 20µm Cloud top 4600'. Peak in CO and O ₃ above cloud top. 82ppb 32ppb
120911	P15↓	descent to 50'			
121625	RS-1	100' run			No drizzle at 100'
122645	P16↑	2500' 100' → 2100'			Drizzle to about 10C ⁻¹ at start of run
122945	RS-2	2500'			
123510					Cloud base dropped a bit in places.
124038	RS-3	4200'			LWC ~ 0.4gm ⁻³ FSSP COP ~ 150cc ⁻¹ MWD 20µm 20C - 30C ⁻¹ ~ 30µm particles
125039	P18↑	4200' → FC100			Peak in CO and O ₃ above cloud top. CO and O ₃ layer ~ 1km thick above cloud top. Neph shows very little aerosol ~ 1µi ³ ⇒ aged aerosol.

P19↓ descent to cloud top from FC100

3. 1/2 mile to point Alpha

Mission Scientist's Log

Do 228 expect West from Alpha 3 1/2 mins 16.602

Flight No B.447 Date 9.11.1988 Name STEVE ASSEL Page 5 of 6

1135
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1995

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
130308	R6.1	4700'			Cloud top run. LWC peaking about 0.5 gm ⁻³ when in cloud top.
131350	R6.2	4700'			In cloud run. X-chat Do 228 going to RIO after previously not able to get right engine fixed up. Drizzle rate core ~ 50L ⁻¹
132351	P21↓				} Arranging co-ordination with Do 228 over X-chat - no radar on this sector
132541	R6.3				
133553	P22↓				
133922	P23↑	50' - 6000'			Profile through cloud LWC peak 0.5 gm ⁻³
134808	R7.1	4600'			Cloud top run - skimming cloud top
135813	R7.2	4000'			CDP ~ 100cc ⁻¹ , MVD 20µm FSSP ~ 150cc ⁻¹ , MVD 21µm 2D-C 30L ⁻¹ 20µm particles w/ typically ± 1ms ⁻¹
140802	P26↓	4000'			Cloud base 3700'
140954	R7.3	2700'			Very little drizzle - occasional small particles
141600					Cloud becoming more patchy
141917	P27↓	down to 50'			Surface wind ~ 4ms ⁻¹ cf to ~ 11ms ⁻¹ further out
142304	P28↑				Profile through cloud. Cloud top LWC ~ 0.2 gm ⁻³
143706	R8.1	3900'			Comparison ^{run} with Do 228. 146 is cloud - very thin LWC ~ 0.1 gm ⁻³ , CDP 150cc ⁻¹ MVD 10µm FSSP 250cc ⁻¹ MVD 10µm.

VOCALS BAe-146 Instrument status Report

Date of report(UTC): 2008/11/09 13:00

Author of report: Grant Allen

Submitted at(UTC): 2008/11/13 22:21

Remaining flight hours: 20

General Comments:

After 20S flight (B417)

INSTRUMENTS/SYSTEMS STATUS

 = no report

Meteorology/Navigation

1.	GPS (Patch)	Comment:	
2.	GPS (Cruciform)	Comment:	
3.	Temperature/Pressure	Comment:	
4.	Water Vapor (Hygrometer)	Comment:	
5.	Turbulence Probe	Comment:	
6.	Altitude (RadarAlt)	Comment:	
7.	Doppler Radar	Comment:	
8.	Dropsonde (AVAPS)	Comment:	Not operated

Radiation

9.	Broadband Radiometer (BBR)	Comment:	
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10.	Spectral Radiometer (ARIES)	Comment:	
11.	In-flight Microwave Obs System (DEIMOS)	Comment:	
12.	Microwave Radiometer Scanning System (MARSS)	Comment:	
13.	Shortwave Spectrometer (SWS)	Comment:	
14.	Spectral Irradiance (SHIM)	Comment:	
15.	Heimann Downward-facing Radiometer	Comment:	

Chemistry

16.	Ozone (CAMP 2B)	Comment:	
17.	NO _x	Comment:	NO ₂ data poor for much of flight due to inlet crud
18.	CO (AL5002)	Comment:	
19.	SO ₂ (TECO 43C)	Comment:	
20.	Sample Bottles (WAS)	Comment:	not carried in VOCALS
21.	CH ₄ /CO ₂ (NIR-TDLAS)	Comment:	
22.	PAN (GC)	Comment:	not operated
23.	Volatile Aerosol Composition (VACC)	Comment:	
24.	CH ₄ /N ₂ O (1C-TDLAS)	Comment:	

Cloud Physics and Aerosol

25.	Liquid and Total water probe	Comment:	
26.	LWC (Johnson Williams)	Comment:	
27.	TWC	Comment:	
28.	FFSSP	Comment:	
29.	2D-C	Comment:	
30.	PCASP	Comment:	believed to still have leak - Ch2 counts substituted for Ch1 counts to generate spectrum/total concs, but concs still too high
31.	Small Ice Detector (SID-2)	Comment:	not fitted
32.	Cloud and Precipitation Imager (CIP-15)	Comment:	needs alignment
33.	Cloud Droplet Probe (CDP)	Comment:	
34.	Condensation Nucleus Counter (CNC)	Comment:	
35.	Cloud Condensation Nuclei Spectrometer (CCNc)	Comment:	only 1 channel working
36.	Fluorescence water vapour sensor (FWVS)	Comment:	
37.	Dry Nephelometer	Comment:	
38.	Wet Nephelometer	Comment:	
39.	Black Carbon (PSAP)	Comment:	
40.	Filters	Comment:	
41.	Aerosol Mass Spectrometer (AMS)	Comment:	

42.	Counter-flow virtual Impactor (CVI)	Comment:	
43.	2-D Imaging Probe (SPEC-2D-S-128H)	Comment:	
44.	CAPS	Comment:	
45.	Single Particle Soot Photometer (SP-2)	Comment:	not fitted
46.	Fine-mode Aerosol Spectrometer (UHSAS)	Comment:	not fitted
47.	Scanning Mobility Particle Sizer (SMPS)	Comment:	
48.	Ultrafine particle counter 1 (LP-WUCPC-1)	Comment:	
49.	Ultrafine particle counter 2 (LP-WUCPC-2)	Comment:	

Other

50.	SATCOM C	Comment:	
51.	SATCOM H	Comment:	
52.	Up, Down, Front, Rear Digital Imagery	Comment:	

[prev](#) | [next](#)

 [Back to VOCALS Field Catalog](#) | [edit](#) | [delete](#)

comments : gstoss at ucar.edu

Chemistry Log

Date: 09 Nov 2008

Flight: B417

Operator:

Doug Anderson

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Preflight

No.	? or x	Location	Action	Comments
<u>Gases</u>				
1	X	CO ₂ / Ar	Outlet pressure is between 2 and 2.5 bar	
2	X	CO ₂ / Ar	Inlet pressure not less than 20 psi	164 / 168
3	X	Nitrogen	Outlet pressure is between 2 and 2.5 bar	
4	X	Nitrogen	Inlet pressure not less than 20 psi, note pressure	44 / 45
5	X	CO standard	Outlet pressure is between 2 and 2.5 bar	
6	X	CO standard	Inlet pressure not less than 20 psi, note pressure	29 / 20
<u>Flows</u>				
7	X	Ozone sample flows	Flow ~ 07. LPM on both channels	
8	X	NOx sample flow	~ 1 LPM	
9	X	NOx Ozonator flow	~ 0.065 LPM	
10	X	CO lamp flow	~ 40 ml/min	
11	X	CO pressure cell	~ 7.5 bar	
12	X	CO pressure monochromator	~ 5 bar	CO time synched @ 08:10:00
<u>Zeros</u>				
13	X	Ozone zero	Performed OK (if not approx zero note values)	
14	X	NOx zero	Performed OK (if not approx zero note values)	
15	X	CO zero	Left for approx 10 min	08:58:04 to 09:20:06
16	X	SO ₂ zero (not for most flights)	Left for approx 10 min	
<u>Other</u>				
17	X	Tubing	All inlets / exhausts connected	
18	X	HORACE data	Check data is being displayed and recorded	
19	No	CO calibration	If unattended set to auto cal (40 min)	
<u>TDLAS</u>				
20	n/a	230V	230V power breakers on	
21	n/a	28V	Red LED on front panel (ensure LTI breaker on)	
22	n/a	Laptop	On and software working	
23	n/a	Data	Being saved to correct directories	

Post flight

<u>Switch Off</u>				
1	X	CO	Switch off instrument	
2	X	Ozone	Switch off monitor	
3	X	NOx	Switch off monitor	
4	X	Pumps	Switch off all pumps	
5	X	Breaker	Pop all breakers on rack and SSP	
<u>Gases (note pressures)</u>				
6	X	CO ₂ /Ar	Close valves and check inlet pressure not below 20 psi	See above.
7	X	CO standard	Close valves and check inlet pressure not below 20 psi	See above.
8	X	Nitrogen	Close valves and check inlet pressure not below 20 psi If below 20 psi then the cylinder needs changing refilling	See above. Refilled post flight
<u>Driers</u>				
9	X	Small drier	Change if spent	
10	X	Large drier	Change if spent	
<u>TDLAS</u>				
11	n/a	Data transfer	To memory stick	
12	n/a	Laptop	Shut down	
13	n/a	Switch off instrument	Pull all breakers IF no other instrument on	
<u>Log</u>				
14	X	Flight Log	Put log in folder (notify Ruth of any issues)	
15	None	Faults	Fill out separate log for in flight issues put in flight folder	
16	n/a	TDLAS data	Send to project spaces on BADC	

Chemistry Log

Date: 09 Nov 2008

Flight: B417

Operator:

Doug Anderson

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In flight

CO calibrations only need carrying out when the lamp temperature changes, if unsure perform a quick cal first.
 During each CO calibration check Ozone and NOx flows are similar to those observed pre-flight

Time	Flight level	CO Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	CO Bkgrd (ppbV)	CO Bkgrd Count (Hz)	CO Cell Pressure (Torr)	CO Lamp Temp (deg C)
09:35:02	Ground, pre power c/o	91.68	305.04	27964.47	39.68	7.52
Time	Flight level	CO Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	CO Bkgrd (ppbV)	CO Bkgrd Count (Hz)	CO Cell Pressure (Torr)	CO Lamp Temp (deg C)
09:43:46	Ground, pre power c/o	91.71	304.09	27887.60	40.24	7.52
Time	Flight level	CO Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	CO Bkgrd (ppbV)	CO Bkgrd Count (Hz)	CO Cell Pressure (Torr)	CO Lamp Temp (deg C)
09:57:27	Ground, during taxi	91.58	303.03	27751.37	40.45	7.52

Flight level	Zero Start time	Zero End time	Counts (Hz)	Span Start time	Span End time	Conc. Range	Counts range	Pressure Cell (Torr)	Lamp Temp	O3 Intensities
6000'	10:05:14	10:06:15	27629 - 28299	10:06:16	10:07:16	513-527	74350 - 75331	7.51	40:48	A: 106917 B: 127914
100'	10:58:13	10:59:15	27601 28208	10:59:17	11:00:17	520 - 543	75666 - 76287	7.56	39:46	A: 94416 B: 112931
2300'	11:45:10	11:46:30	27576 - 28198	11:47:40	11:48:40	528 - 543	76387 - 77587	7.49	38.60	A: 93287 B: 111581
2300'	12:36:40	12:37:40	27475 - 28234	12:37:40	12:38:40	521 - 539	76220 - 77500	7.59	38.5	A: B:
2500'	13:28:15	13:29:15	27329 - 27924	13:29:16	13:30:16	522 - 537	75494 - 76931	7.51	38.11	A: 92919 B: 111164
3800'	14:06:40	14:08:02	Canx -	reducing altitude						A: B:
2700'	14:09:11	14:10:34	27307 - 27849	14:10:37	14:11:37	523 - 539	75931 - 76753	7.51	38.14	A: 92935 B: 111181
3800'	14:49:30	14:50:30	27340 - 27977	14:50:33	14:51:33	520 - 537	75779 - 76651	7.51	38.14	A: 92993 B: 111269
Post Flight	after G3	comparison:								A: B:
Ground, post power changeover	16:52:00	16:53:00	26662 - 27103	16:53:02	16:54:003	489 - 503	72202 - 72555	7.50	40.53	A: 103507 B: 123968

Post flight intercomparison with G3

Time	Flight level	CO Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	CO Bkgrd (ppbV)	CO Bkgrd Count (Hz)	CO Cell Pressure (Torr)	CO Lamp Temp (deg C)
16:58:26	Ground, post power c/o	87.71	306.05	26842.63	40.54	7.51
Time	Flight level	CO Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	CO Bkgrd (ppbV)	CO Bkgrd Count (Hz)	CO Cell Pressure (Torr)	CO Lamp Temp (deg C)
17:02:14	Ground, post power c/o	87.16	308.22	26863.47	40.57	7.53
Time	Flight level	CO Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	CO Bkgrd (ppbV)	CO Bkgrd Count (Hz)	CO Cell Pressure (Torr)	CO Lamp Temp (deg C)

In flight comments

O3 'B' intensities:
 09:58:45 128947 (take off)
 10:00:00 129397 (1000')
 10:04:45 129370 (6000')

SIZE	#	CHARGED	FLIGHT/DATE	DISCHARGED	COMMENTS
10	1	4/11 KOB	B417	9/11 HC	
1	2	"	B417	9/11 HC	
10	7	5/11 KOB	B417	9/11 HC	
1	8	5/11 KOB	B417	9/11 HC	
10	10	5/11 KOB	B417	9/11 HC	SOME RESIDUE ON FILTER
1	69	5/11 KOB	B417	9/11 HC	
10	33	5/11 KOB	B417	9/11 HC	
1	40	5/11 KOB	B417	9/11 HC	

B417

FILTER #	LAC ^W	T _{OP}	Time Off.	RUN	TOTAL VOL(L)
7, 8, 117	U	10:21	10:35	r2.1	840
"	"	10:56	11:19	r3.1	1109
1, 2, 44	U	11:44	11:56	r4.1	655
33, 40, no N ^S	U	12:18	12:26	r5.1	589
"	"	12:29	12:39	r5.2	1151
10, 09, 152	U	13:29	13:42	r6.3	750
"	"	14:14	14:27	r7.3	759
"	"	14:53	15:05	?	726

log frozen.
 R8.3 start as end P31
 R8.2 2200ft. 145750
 R8.3 end.
 P32 145949
 50ft. 150252
 P33.
 5000ft.

land Area

15:23:44

B417

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B417

Date: 09/11/08

Instruments

Dropsondes	nil
CVI -	ok
Filters	ok
Neph	ok
PSAP	ok
WetNeph	ok
AMS	ok
Core Chem	ok
Cloud physics -	ok PCASP channel 1 noisy otherwise scale error (leak) Ok FFSSP one hard disc fallover - minutes data loss
ARIES -	ok
MARSS -	ok
SWS -	ok
CCN	ok, single channel only
VACC -	ok – needs mirror cleaning
2DS -	ok, - one run lost by data hang
CAPS -	ok,
SMPS -	ok
Buck -	experimental operation ->ok

Aircraft

SatcomC weather data not received, other ops normal

ISDN Emails

Nil

MPDS

Run for flight, ok

Satcom-H Calls

nil

Issues

Flight manager's log froze at P31 – completed by hand
GIN went walkabout before flight, stabilised after reset after take off

Satcom C did not receive weather reports even though emails were going successfully[???

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 09/11/2008

Flight No: B 417

Pre-Flighter: JT

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	☒	Hangar	Collect spanners for core chem	N/A
<u>Aircraft Cabin: Power-up</u>				
2	☒	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	N ₂ V. LOW 30 bars.
3	☒	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	☒	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
5	☒	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	40 min ⁻¹ , 5.17, 7.51, 5.17
6	☒	Aft CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
7	☒	Fore CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
8	☒	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
9	☒	HORACE	Recording data	
10	☒	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	11VDLU - NO Pkts.
11	☒	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
12	☒	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
13	☒	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
14	☒	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	NO REWARD FACING CAM
15	☒	Video Laptop	Checked onboard	NOT ON BOARD
16	☒	FWVS	Set up & check on AUTO	
17	☒	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked then OFF	Submit log for non-11ms
18	☒	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
19	☒	TWC	Fitted & signals checked	
20	☒	GE	Balance checked then back to DP	
21	☒	GPS (XR5M)	Checked	
22	☒	Satcom C	Checked	
23	☒	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	N/A.

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
24	☐	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	In cockpit
25	☒	CNC	Butanol filled	N/A
26	☒	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	
27	☒	PSAP	Pre-flight log actions complete	JTB OPERATOR
28	☒	CGPS	CBs and PC ON	NON-OP.
<u>External Checks</u>				
29	☒	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
30	☒	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	☒	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	☒	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	☒	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
34	☒	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	☒	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
36	☒	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	☒	Heimann	Lens checked OK	DARK OUTSIDE
38	☒	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	NOT ON, NICE WEATHER
39	☒	All other covers	Removed	
40	☐	Pre-flight Bag	Returned to hold	** Check no butanol**
41	☐	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
42	☐	Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				
44	☒	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		Signed NO SAFE ACCESS
45	☐	ICEX applied		
46	☐	Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -		a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) 1/4 full or more
47	☐	Turb Probe - Traps dried and resealed		

CVI log

11/9/08 8:43:25 AM
11/9/08 8:43:37 AM pcasp ~300 before turning pumps on
11/9/08 8:52:00 AM pcasp ~300 before turning pumps on
11/9/08 8:52:35 AM pcasp ~300 before turning pumps on
11/9/08 8:53:07 AM pcasp ~300 before turning pumps on
11/9/08 8:53:52 AM pcasp ~300 before turning pumps on
11/9/08 9:16:02 AM lyman alpha turned on
11/9/08 9:16:12 AM noise on pcasp?
11/9/08 9:17:44 AM could be turbulence at the tip due to the high counterflow
11/9/08 9:25:32 AM dodgy tas at the minute we are stopped on the ground at 4m/s
11/9/08 9:39:46 AM lyman zero'd
11/9/08 9:40:36 AM temperatures are too high on PIDS - might sort itself out in the
air
11/9/08 9:40:49 AM ready for take off
11/9/08 10:05:36 AM
11/9/08 10:05:57 AM A NEW LYMAN ZERO
11/9/08 10:06:16 AM lyman to sample line
11/9/08 10:08:56 AM reduce counterflow for cloud passage
11/9/08 10:09:03 AM reduce counterflow for cloud passage
11/9/08 10:09:26 AM set INC flow to -0.5 for the duration - this is to account for
the offset in the counterflow calibration
11/9/08 10:15:54 AM go to aerosol mode
11/9/08 10:18:29 AM cpc similar to the cpc on the CNC rack
11/9/08 10:28:35 AM cpc similar to the cpc on the CNC rack
11/9/08 10:28:39 AM cpc similar to the cpc on the CNC rack
11/9/08 10:29:54 AM both manchester instruments on cvi now
11/9/08 10:30:04 AM change the flows settings
11/9/08 10:30:30 AM ams to 0.72
11/9/08 10:30:37 AM sp2/cpi to 1.0
11/9/08 10:31:27 AM sp2/cpi to 1.0
11/9/08 10:31:44 AM increase L control
11/9/08 10:31:48 AM increase L control
11/9/08 10:31:52 AM increase L control
11/9/08 10:31:57 AM increase L control
11/9/08 10:34:07 AM zero achieved at 2.3
11/9/08 10:34:14 AM add 2.5 on just to be sure
11/9/08 10:35:12 AM add 2.5 on just to be sure
11/9/08 10:35:18 AM add 2.5 on just to be sure
11/9/08 10:35:21 AM add 2.5 on just to be sure
11/9/08 10:35:32 AM add 2.5 on just to be sure
11/9/08 10:36:01 AM correction - set cf TO 2.3
11/9/08 10:36:21 AM PARTICLES NOW
11/9/08 10:37:10 AM IN CLOUD NOW
11/9/08 10:37:33 AM
11/9/08 10:37:37 AM
11/9/08 10:38:18 AM drop counterflow to 1.8
11/9/08 10:40:25 AM drop L control - very small particles
11/9/08 10:40:30 AM high concentrations
11/9/08 10:46:33 AM high concentrations
11/9/08 10:46:36 AM high concentrations
11/9/08 10:46:40 AM high concentrations
11/9/08 10:50:17 AM into cvi mode just for cloud passge
11/9/08 10:50:54 AM into cvi mode just for cloud passge
11/9/08 10:51:04 AM into cvi mode just for cloud passge
11/9/08 10:52:12 AM into cvi mode just for cloud passge
11/9/08 10:52:24 AM out of cvi mode
11/9/08 10:52:50 AM using and l of 0.1 and the flows of 0.72, 1.0, -0.5 gives more
sensible values
11/9/08 10:59:44 AM alter pcasp flows
11/9/08 11:04:31 AM if total sample flow is wrong then ef is wrong, and
concentrations are wrong
11/9/08 11:05:03 AM we can correct for this in post flight processing
11/9/08 11:09:10 AM in the current situation - the smple flow is reduced and so, ef
will be lower than quoted on the front panel
11/9/08 11:09:41 AM SO - ALL IN CLOUD COUNTS, LWC, PARTICLES CONCS WILL BE HIGHER
THAN THE ACTUAL READ OUT
11/9/08 11:09:53 AM THINGS MIGHT NOT BE SO BAD AS PREVIOUSLY THOUGH

11/9/08 11:11:29 AM VARIABLE CLOUD ABOVE - SWS
11/9/08 11:11:35 AM DRIZZLE AS WELL
11/9/08 11:13:04 AM
11/9/08 11:16:48 AM shattering on inlet - drizzle? large increase in cpc
11/9/08 11:19:12 AM lots of counts on cpc
11/9/08 11:19:29 AM a bit more motion on the w component
11/9/08 11:20:36 AM into cvi mode now
11/9/08 11:20:48 AM ams and 2ps on cvi now
11/9/08 11:20:53 AM alter the flow dials
11/9/08 11:21:00 AM alter the flow dials
11/9/08 11:21:03 AM alter the flow dials
11/9/08 11:21:07 AM alter the flow dials
11/9/08 11:21:44 AM lot of shaterinf
11/9/08 11:23:27 AM lot of shaterinf
11/9/08 11:23:33 AM lot of shaterinf
11/9/08 11:23:41 AM lot of shaterinf
11/9/08 11:23:45 AM lot of shaterinf
11/9/08 11:27:09 AM lot of shaterinf
11/9/08 11:27:49 AM lot of shaterinf
11/9/08 11:29:43 AM sp2 off cvi
11/9/08 11:29:49 AM all counts start to fall
11/9/08 11:30:20 AM reduce flow dial to sp2 back to zero
11/9/08 11:30:26 AM this is a test of organics
11/9/08 11:31:13 AM this is a test of organics
11/9/08 11:31:17 AM this is a test of organics
11/9/08 11:31:36 AM this is a test of organics
11/9/08 11:35:07 AM cvi to aerosol mode
11/9/08 11:40:31 AM drizzle problems on this profile down
11/9/08 11:40:40 AM
11/9/08 11:40:45 AM
11/9/08 11:40:49 AM
11/9/08 11:40:52 AM
11/9/08 11:40:55 AM
11/9/08 11:45:23 AM shattering
11/9/08 11:48:13 AM shattering? only 1 or 2 on 2d
11/9/08 11:49:48 AM seeing lots of particles but thre l
11/9/08 11:50:02 AM but the lwc is falling slowly through the run
11/9/08 11:52:02 AM LOTS of structure on the particle counters
11/9/08 11:52:09 AM nothing on cwc
11/9/08 11:52:13 AM nothing on cwc
11/9/08 11:52:15 AM nothing on cwc
11/9/08 11:53:35 AM sp2 on cvi
11/9/08 11:53:44 AM waiting for ams
11/9/08 11:53:51 AM ams on cvi now
11/9/08 11:54:03 AM ams on cvi now
11/9/08 11:54:09 AM ams on cvi now
11/9/08 11:54:13 AM ams on cvi now
11/9/08 11:56:40 AM cant get a zero on the cvi - do we hace a leak?
11/9/08 11:57:08 AM cant get a zero on the cvi - do we hace a leak?
11/9/08 11:57:14 AM cant get a zero on the cvi - do we hace a leak?
11/9/08 11:57:32 AM nudge l contrl
11/9/08 11:57:39 AM L=1.7y
11/9/08 11:57:45 AM l indicator is now 1.0mm
11/9/08 11:58:01 AM l indicator is now 1.0mm
11/9/08 11:58:06 AM l indicator is now 1.0mm
11/9/08 11:58:10 AM l indicator is now 1.0mm
11/9/08 11:58:13 AM l indicator is now 1.0mm
11/9/08 11:58:17 AM l indicator is now 1.0mm
11/9/08 12:02:24 PM l indicator is now 1.0mm
11/9/08 12:05:55 PM mean volume radius indicator? complicated by the fact that we
will miss a lot of the clud below $7\mu\text{m}$ - assume a distribution below that
level - souldn't be too bad as most lwc above
11/9/08 12:06:15 PM should cpc conc be so high?
11/9/08 12:06:41 PM should cpc conc be so high?
11/9/08 12:06:51 PM should cpc conc be so high?
11/9/08 12:07:07 PM should cpc conc be so high?
11/9/08 12:07:12 PM should cpc conc be so high?
11/9/08 12:07:37 PM climbing through cloud
11/9/08 12:08:51 PM back into aewrosol mode

11/9/08 12:09:37 PM turn hygro to aerosol for cloud passage
11/9/08 12:11:45 PM hygro back to sample
11/9/08 12:14:56 PM cpc counts, seem to pick up stuff that the cpc on the cnc rack does not, is this shattering, stray drizzle particles or what?
11/9/08 12:15:24 PM cpc counts, seem to pick up stuff that the cpc on the cnc rack does not, is this shattering, stray drizzle particles or what?
11/9/08 12:15:28 PM cpc counts, seem to pick up stuff that the cpc on the cnc rack does not, is this shattering, stray drizzle particles or what?
11/9/08 12:15:33 PM cpc counts, seem to pick up stuff that the cpc on the cnc rack does not, is this shattering, stray drizzle particles or what?
11/9/08 12:15:37 PM cpc counts, seem to pick up stuff that the cpc on the cnc rack does not, is this shattering, stray drizzle particles or what?
11/9/08 12:23:09 PM spike in cpc data
11/9/08 12:23:31 PM spike in cpc data
11/9/08 12:23:38 PM spike in cpc data
11/9/08 12:24:51 PM spike in cpc data
11/9/08 12:24:55 PM spike in cpc data
11/9/08 12:28:59 PM drizzle shattering again?
11/9/08 12:30:45 PM cloud physics - 10per litre
11/9/08 12:30:59 PM so we do pick it up on cvi in aerosol mode
11/9/08 12:38:55 PM ams on to cvi inlet
11/9/08 12:38:58 PM counterflow on
11/9/08 12:39:41 PM counterflow on
11/9/08 12:39:47 PM counterflow on
11/9/08 12:42:53 PM how much of the drizzle can we collect? will it shatter
11/9/08 12:45:50 PM how much of the drizzle can we collect? will it shatter
11/9/08 12:45:59 PM how much of the drizzle can we collect? will it shatter
11/9/08 12:46:15 PM how much of the drizzle can we collect? will it shatter
11/9/08 12:51:39 PM ams switching back now
11/9/08 12:51:51 PM get smps data from ams
11/9/08 12:52:02 PM back to aerosol mode
11/9/08 12:54:14 PM back to aerosol mode
11/9/08 12:57:02 PM profile up completed
11/9/08 12:57:15 PM switch lyman to counterflow, adn do a zero
11/9/08 12:59:02 PM lyman zero'd
11/9/08 12:59:22 PM lyman back to sample
11/9/08 12:59:50 PM counterflow ON, AMS is on Rosemount! remove AMS flow from the dial
11/9/08 12:59:52 PM counterflow ON, AMS is on Rosemount! remove AMS flow from the dial
11/9/08 1:01:05 PM turn counterflow up a bit, not quite getting a zero
11/9/08 1:01:50 PM turn counterflow up a bit, not quite getting a zero still...
11/9/08 1:02:48 PM turn counterflow up a bit, not quite getting a zero still...
11/9/08 1:02:59 PM AMS is back on cloud - into cvi mode!
11/9/08 1:03:14 PM set up as previous now
11/9/08 1:03:49 PM set up as previous now
11/9/08 1:03:53 PM set up as previous now
11/9/08 1:03:56 PM set up as previous now
11/9/08 1:04:01 PM set up as previous now
11/9/08 1:04:05 PM set up as previous now
11/9/08 1:04:59 PM fantastic structure on the lyman, and concetrations
11/9/08 1:05:50 PM fantastic structure on the lyman, and concetrations
11/9/08 1:08:14 PM fantastic structure on the lyman, and concetrations
11/9/08 1:08:19 PM fantastic structure on the lyman, and concetrations
11/9/08 1:11:56 PM fantastic structure on the lyman, and concetrations
11/9/08 1:12:00 PM fantastic structure on the lyman, and concetrations
11/9/08 1:12:06 PM fantastic structure on the lyman, and concetrations
11/9/08 1:14:22 PM start of main in cloud run
11/9/08 1:16:49 PM start of main in cloud run
11/9/08 1:17:10 PM start of main in cloud run
11/9/08 1:18:22 PM start of main in cloud run
11/9/08 1:18:36 PM start of main in cloud run
11/9/08 1:18:57 PM start of main in cloud run
11/9/08 1:20:50 PM start of main in cloud run
11/9/08 1:21:11 PM start of main in cloud run
11/9/08 1:21:18 PM start of main in cloud run
11/9/08 1:21:31 PM start of main in cloud run
11/9/08 1:21:38 PM start of main in cloud run
11/9/08 1:21:42 PM start of main in cloud run

11/9/08 1:24:22 PM start of main in cloud run
11/9/08 1:24:36 PM start of main in cloud run
11/9/08 1:25:04 PM out of cloud, into aerosol mode
11/9/08 1:25:35 PM out of cloud, into aerosol mode
11/9/08 1:25:52 PM cvi into cloud mode to try and sample the drizzle
11/9/08 1:26:21 PM aerosol measurements are no good at this altitude just below cloud base
11/9/08 1:28:23 PM still have high lwc even below cloud
11/9/08 1:29:27 PM it does not look like we have drizzle
11/9/08 1:29:44 PM we still have counts and water around here - is it large wet aerosol?
11/9/08 1:31:12 PM lwc is falling - are we simply drying the pipework out?
11/9/08 1:32:24 PM
11/9/08 1:32:36 PM
11/9/08 1:32:42 PM
11/9/08 1:32:49 PM
11/9/08 1:32:57 PM
11/9/08 1:33:01 PM
11/9/08 1:36:04 PM
11/9/08 1:36:07 PM
11/9/08 1:36:43 PM
11/9/08 1:36:48 PM
11/9/08 1:36:54 PM
11/9/08 1:37:00 PM
11/9/08 1:37:04 PM
11/9/08 1:37:26 PM into aerosol mode
11/9/08 1:40:05 PM into aerosol mode
11/9/08 1:40:42 PM does the TWC probe dry the water off the aerosol probes as well as vapour, lwc
11/9/08 1:40:55 PM that might account for higher water values from the CVI
11/9/08 1:42:36 PM lyman inlet closed for cloud passages
11/9/08 1:42:40 PM passage
11/9/08 1:44:22 PM cloud top, lyman back to sample
11/9/08 1:44:30 PM switch to cvi at top of profile
11/9/08 1:45:42 PM switch to cvi at top of profile
11/9/08 1:46:29 PM switch to cvi at top of profile
11/9/08 1:47:05 PM ams into cvi mode
11/9/08 1:48:18 PM ams into cvi mode
11/9/08 1:48:22 PM ams into cvi mode
11/9/08 1:49:13 PM ams into cvi mode
11/9/08 1:49:32 PM seeing cloud top structure again,
11/9/08 1:49:59 PM smaller cells than we saw on the lastrun
11/9/08 1:58:55 PM ams came on then off - thought we were doing sub cloud not in cloud! ONLY FOR A FEW SECONDS!
11/9/08 2:04:22 PM is cloud top falling? getting brighter above
11/9/08 2:06:53 PM two step changes in this leg, of increasing lwc
11/9/08 2:07:37 PM into aerosol mode for the sub cloud leg
11/9/08 2:07:46 PM expect shattering of drizzle drops
11/9/08 2:08:47 PM lwc falling off as drop through cloud
11/9/08 2:08:55 PM into aerosol mode now
11/9/08 2:09:56 PM lots of structure to cpc counts indicating drizzle
11/9/08 2:10:10 PM we are not very far below cloud base here
11/9/08 2:10:27 PM cloud base = 3250
11/9/08 2:12:38 PM some spikes in cpc
11/9/08 2:15:13 PM some spikes in cpc again now
11/9/08 2:15:28 PM some spikes in cpc again now
11/9/08 2:15:32 PM some spikes in cpc again now
11/9/08 2:19:11 PM start of profile
11/9/08 2:20:43 PM increase dilution factor
11/9/08 2:26:30 PM in cloud - lyman to counterflow
11/9/08 2:27:22 PM lyman back to sample
11/9/08 2:27:29 PM into cvi at the top of the profile
11/9/08 2:29:43 PM into counterflow now
11/9/08 2:30:08 PM ams joined us on cvi
11/9/08 2:30:18 PM ams joined us on cvi
11/9/08 2:30:28 PM ams joined us on cvi
11/9/08 2:30:32 PM ams joined us on cvi
11/9/08 2:30:36 PM ams joined us on cvi
11/9/08 2:31:49 PM in cloud 0- holes to sea surface

11/9/08 2:32:51 PM
11/9/08 2:36:22 PM
11/9/08 2:36:28 PM
11/9/08 2:36:35 PM
11/9/08 2:43:23 PM
11/9/08 2:43:27 PM
11/9/08 2:43:30 PM
11/9/08 2:43:34 PM
11/9/08 2:43:38 PM
11/9/08 2:43:42 PM
11/9/08 2:46:34 PM
11/9/08 2:46:38 PM
11/9/08 2:48:39 PM
11/9/08 2:49:01 PM into aerosol mode now
11/9/08 2:49:36 PM last below cloud run
11/9/08 2:49:57 PM last below cloud run
11/9/08 2:51:42 PM stable cpc at this region near to coast thinner cloud not as much
drizzle to contaminate the aerosol measurements
11/9/08 2:52:13 PM stable cpc at this region near to coast thinner cloud not as much
drizzle to contaminate the aerosol measurements
11/9/08 2:52:17 PM stable cpc at this region near to coast thinner cloud not as much
drizzle to contaminate the aerosol measurements
11/9/08 2:52:20 PM stable cpc at this region near to coast thinner cloud not as much
drizzle to contaminate the aerosol measurements
11/9/08 2:54:29 PM at end of run, into aerosol mode, lyman to counterflow, resady
for landing, and zero on the ground for the hygro
11/9/08 2:55:35 PM lots of structure in cpc
11/9/08 2:56:33 PM dropping to avoid cloud
11/9/08 2:57:23 PM going through pockets below the main layer - cu at the lower
mini-inversion
11/9/08 2:59:51 PM we are now going to fit in a descent and ascent to 6.0kft before
end of science
11/9/08 3:00:47 PM we are now going to fit in a descent and ascent to 6.0kft before
end of science
11/9/08 3:05:37 PM fluffy cumulus on ascent, leave lyman as is until top of profile
11/9/08 3:07:48 PM counterflow back onm turn it up to 5
11/9/08 3:07:57 PM end of science
11/9/08 3:08:06 PM lyman to counterflow air
11/9/08 3:29:46 PM zero lyman.
11/9/08 3:31:08 PM turn off and back on for intercomparison

ARIES flight log

Flight: B417

page 1 of 2

Date: 09/Nov/2003

Operator(s): S. Rogers

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: VOCALS

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop_DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
20805	On the ground						Power on OK
083430	"		CH	C	71	31	ColdHotIn.scrpt.
095857	TAKE OFF P1↑		—	C	71	31	—
100459	6000ft		NZ	O	71	31	Nad Zen Long Run 30 sec End to 09
101051	↓						6000ft → 50ft.
101849	500ft		NZ	O	71	30	Nad Zen Long Run 30 sec ⁽¹⁾ 718 Sec above
1024	↑			O	71	31	500ft → 1000 ft
102853	1000ft	1.					
103408	↑		—	C	71	31	End of (V) Climb to 2900ft
1049	↓						6000ft → 50ft
105600	↓		N	C	71	31	Nadir Long Run 3 min
105643	100ft ^{3.1}			C	71	30	
110601	"	120x1	Z	O	71	31	Zenith 718 Sec above
110705	↑ "		CH	C	71	30	ColdHotIn.scrpt.
111000	2500ft		NZ	O	71	30	Nad Zen Long Run 30 sec
	3500ft			C			in cloud
112129	"		CH	C	71	30	ColdHotIn
114040	↓		N	C	71	31	Nadir Long Run 3 min Down to 50ft
114257	↑		CH	C	71	30	ColdHotIn
1145	2500ft		NZ	O	71	31	Nad Zen Long Run 30 sec
115608	↑			C	71	30	Up to 3700ft
121050	↓		N	C	71	30	2000 6000ft → 50ft
121550	100ft		N	C	71	30	Nadir Long Run 3 min
122553	"	420x1	Z	O	71	31	Zenith
122655	↑		CH	C	71	31	ColdHotIn
122915	2500ft		NZ	O	71	31	Nad Zen Long Run 30 sec.
1232							Banking 79° 51' W
123523			NZ	O	71	31	Nad Zen Long Run 30 sec. to 123843
130320	4700ft		Z	O	71	31	Zenith Long Run 3 min Skimming cloud by 6.0 sec
132550	2500ft		NZ	O	71	31	Nad Zen Long Run 30 sec.
	↓						to 50ft

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG	Date	9/11/08	Flight	B417	log pages
Operator(s)	Jeff Norwood-Brown		Campaign	VOCALS	
Departure			Arrival		

**System start
MARSS**

Visual pod inspection						•
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						•
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						•
FERA on	at time					
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	18.1°C	Ch 17	18.0°C	Ch18	18.2°C
Temperature controller set points		54°C		58°C	-20	40°C
MARSS CPU on	at time					0808
Initial target temperatures	Hot	291.2	Cold	290.0		
Target heating						•
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						•
Scanning on (LMD box)	at time					
Scan indication	Monitor •			Visual •		

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers						
Turn on Deimos CPU						
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						
Start Deimos Software	at time					
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold			
Target heating						
Scan indication	Monitor			Visual		
Weather	Cloud		Precip			
	Surface		Pressure			
	Other					

System functionality check (after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} +$	0	at time			
Brightness temps 'sensible'						•
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	Cold			
	Deimos:	Hot	Cold			
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A (-)	Ch3 A (-)	Ch1 B (-)	Ch3 B (-)		
	Ch16 (40-44)	Ch17 (45-49)	Ch18 (40-44)	Ch19 (40-44)	Ch20 (44-48)	

Power changeover

Headset on before start						•
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.					•
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)						•
Exit Deimos Software (x)						
POWER CHANGEOVER						
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton					•
Restart Deimos Software						
System running again	at time					

Wet Nephelometer Log

Flight No **B417.**

Date 09/11/2008..

Operator's name JB.....

Page .1..... of

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
10:16	p2					42		chiller on
10:22	r2.1	500	15	42	78	44		
10:25	"							pre heat off
10:25	"	"	"	46	82	12		
10:31	r2.2	1000	"	49	58	44		
10:58	r3.1	100	15	47	83	12		
11:06	p8		14.8	44	53	44		
11:12	r3.2	2500	14.6	40	83	10		
11:18	r3.2	2500			53	44		
11:46	r4.1	2300	15	40	86	16		
11:54	"			41	51	44		
12:18	r5.1	100	14.5	49	83	15		
12:27	p16		13.6			44		
12:51	p18		13			/		chiller off @ 5000ft profile to 10000
								leave chiller off for next two cloud runs, no incloud neff data
13:22	r6.2					42		chiller on ready for below cloud run.
13:32	r6.3	2300	14.6	43	80	44		
13:33	"	"	"	"	86	10		
13:45	p23							chiller off @5000ft leave off for cloud tops and in cloud runs.
14:03	r7.2	3800	14.4	39	41			chiller back on
14:17	r7.3	2700	14.9	45	45	44		

B417_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog.txt

```

08:05:07.44 --- - - - -
08:05:07.44 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
08:05:07.44 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
08:05:07.44 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B417
08:05:07.44 --- - - - -
08:05:14.96 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
08:05:23.85 SWS -0.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
08:05:24.41 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope stopped.
08:05:25.81 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
08:05:27.47 SWS 169.5 - - - - Telescope stopped.
08:05:30.59 SWS - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
08:05:35.94 USH - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
08:05:39.27 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
08:05:40.62 LSH - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
08:05:40.65 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
08:05:42.90 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
08:05:46.21 SWS - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
08:05:49.86 SWS - - 50 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
08:05:49.86 SWS - - - 50 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
08:05:51.83 USH - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
08:05:55.93 USH - - 50 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
08:05:55.94 USH - - - 50 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
08:05:58.14 LSH - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
08:06:01.91 LSH - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
08:06:01.92 LSH - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
08:06:03.98 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:06:03.99 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:06:04.00 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:06:12.51 USH - - - - Idling
08:06:12.52 SWS - - - - Idling
08:06:12.60 LSH - - - - Idling
08:06:36.06 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:06:36.07 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:06:36.07 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:06:36.60 LSH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
08:06:37.01 USH - - - - Idling
08:06:37.41 SWS - - - - Idling
08:06:37.72 LSH - - - - Idling
08:22:16.82 --- - - - - *** 19 deg
08:23:24.96 --- - - - - *** 18 deg
08:26:16.27 --- - - - - *** 17 deg
08:33:26.04 --- - - - - *** 16 deg
08:37:57.71 --- - - - - *** 15 deg
08:41:58.54 --- - - - - *** 14 deg
09:23:03.05 --- - - - - *** 16 deg
09:31:51.22 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:31:51.23 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:31:51.24 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:31:52.53 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:31:54.83 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
09:31:59.64 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:31:59.66 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:31:59.72 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:32:00.17 LSH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
09:32:00.60 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:32:01.02 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:32:01.30 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:32:03.08 USH - - - - Idling
09:32:03.14 LSH - - - - Idling
09:32:03.19 SWS - - - - Idling
09:32:10.19 --- - - - - *** 16 deg
09:35:33.56 --- - - - - *** 15 deg
09:41:13.69 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:41:13.70 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:41:13.70 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:41:23.74 SWS - - - - Idling

```


10:03:26.65	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:03:26.71	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:03:27.02	SWS	90.0	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
10:03:28.17	SWS	-6.0	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:03:30.18	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:03:30.26	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:03:30.27	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:03:30.52	LSH	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:03:31.36	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:03:31.56	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:03:31.65	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:04:40.60	---	-	-	-	*** run 1
10:06:19.14	---	-	-	-	*** 18 deg
10:07:50.07	---	-	-	-	*** 17 deg
10:10:11.53	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:10:12.54	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:10:13.73	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:10:14.69	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:10:51.70	---	-	-	-	*** profile descent to 50 ft
10:11:08.01	---	-	-	-	*** profile 2
10:11:38.35	USH	-	-	-	Idling
10:11:38.37	SWS	-	-	-	Idling
10:11:38.43	LSH	-	-	-	Idling
10:11:40.19	SWS	-6.0	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
10:11:41.90	SWS	172.9	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:11:43.06	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:11:43.07	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:11:43.08	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:13:26.69	---	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
10:13:44.52	---	-	-	-	*** cloud top 3600 ft
10:15:00.25	---	-	-	-	*** now below cloud
10:17:19.13	---	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
10:17:42.70	---	-	-	-	*** at 50 ft will change telescope
10:17:47.93	SWS	174.0	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
10:17:49.67	SWS	-5.8	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:17:51.64	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:17:51.67	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:17:51.73	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:17:52.45	LSH	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:17:52.73	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:17:52.91	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:17:53.60	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:18:20.17	---	-	-	-	*** run at 500 ft
10:18:36.64	---	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:18:40.12	---	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:20:26.66	---	-	-	-	*** run 2.1
10:21:25.29	---	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
10:28:26.30	---	-	-	-	*** end of run profile ascent to 1500 ft
10:28:29.67	---	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
10:28:59.30	---	-	-	-	*** run at 100 ft
10:29:03.72	---	-	-	-	*** 1000 ft
10:29:14.70	---	-	-	-	*** run 2.2, below cloud run
10:34:09.19	---	-	-	-	*** end of run
10:34:21.65	---	-	-	-	*** profile climb to 2900 ft for in cloud run
10:34:42.71	---	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
10:35:26.05	---	-	-	-	*** LSH VIS recovered
10:35:31.91	---	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
10:37:24.73	---	-	-	-	*** 14 deg and start run 2.3 at 3
10:37:30.14	---	-	-	-	*** 3800 ft
10:38:12.40	---	-	-	-	*** very thin clod dropping down to 3700ft
10:39:42.27	---	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:39:46.38	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:39:46.42	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:39:46.45	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:39:47.61	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:39:47.76	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:39:47.91	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:39:48.93	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:39:48.95	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.


```

11:00:55.20 SWS      -    -    -    -    Manual scene recording started.
11:00:55.50 LSH      -    -    -    -    Manual scene recording started.
11:00:57.39 SWS 174.0 -    -    -    -    Telescope sent to -6.000
11:00:59.12 SWS   -5.7 -    -    -    -    Telescope stopped.
11:01:01.53 USH      -    -    -    -    Dark measurement started.
11:01:01.56 LSH      -    -    -    -    Dark measurement started.
11:01:01.58 SWS      -    -    -    -    Dark measurement started.
11:01:02.49 USH      -    -    -    -    Manual scene recording started.
11:01:02.91 SWS      -    -    -    -    Manual scene recording started.
11:01:03.21 LSH      -    -    -    -    Manual scene recording started.
11:06:25.55 SWS      -    -    -    -    Dark measurement started.
11:06:25.57 LSH      -    -    -    -    Dark measurement started.
11:06:25.60 USH      -    -    -    -    Dark measurement started.
11:06:26.52 SWS      -    -    -    -    Manual scene recording started.
11:06:26.94 USH      -    -    -    -    Manual scene recording started.
11:06:26.97 SWS      -    -    -    -    Dark measurement started.
11:06:27.27 LSH      -    -    -    -    Manual scene recording started.
11:06:28.13 SWS      -    -    -    -    Manual scene recording started.
11:06:59.07 ---      -    -    -    -    *** end of run start of profile ascent
11:09:49.62 ---      -    -    -    -    *** end of profile 8 and start of run 3.2
below cloud run
11:09:54.85 ---      -    -    -    -    *** at 2900 ft
11:10:28.66 ---      -    -    -    -    *** going down 2500 ft
11:20:00.80 ---      -    -    -    -    *** end of run profile ascent for in cloud run
11:21:07.85 ---      -    -    -    -    *** end of profile 9 start of run 3.3
11:21:14.90 ---      -    -    -    -    *** at 3500 ft in cloud
11:23:52.88 SWS  -6.0 -    -    -    -    Telescope sent to 174.000
11:23:54.61 SWS 173.8 -    -    -    -    Telescope stopped.
11:23:57.20 SWS      -    -    -    -    Dark measurement started.
11:23:57.21 LSH      -    -    -    -    Dark measurement started.
11:23:57.25 USH      -    -    -    -    Dark measurement started.
11:23:58.16 SWS      -    -    -    -    Manual scene recording started.
11:23:58.61 USH      -    -    -    -    Manual scene recording started.
11:23:58.90 LSH      -    -    -    -    Manual scene recording started.
11:24:01.48 USH      -    -    -    -    Dark measurement started.
11:24:01.50 LSH      -    -    -    -    Dark measurement started.
11:24:01.54 SWS      -    -    -    -    Dark measurement started.
11:24:02.48 USH      -    -    -    -    Manual scene recording started.
11:24:02.92 SWS      -    -    -    -    Manual scene recording started.
11:24:03.23 LSH      -    -    -    -    Manual scene recording started.
11:27:52.38 SWS 174.0 -    -    -    -    Telescope sent to -6.000
11:27:54.13 SWS  -5.7 -    -    -    -    Telescope stopped.
11:28:01.96 LSH      -    -    -    -    Dark measurement started.
11:28:01.97 SWS      -    -    -    -    Dark measurement started.
11:28:02.01 USH      -    -    -    -    Dark measurement started.
11:28:03.11 SWS      -    -    -    -    Manual scene recording started.
11:28:03.33 USH      -    -    -    -    Manual scene recording started.
11:28:03.42 LSH      -    -    -    -    Manual scene recording started.
11:31:04.69 ---      -    -    -    -    *** 16 deg
11:32:50.23 ---      -    -    -    -    *** end of run start of profile ascent to
above cloud
11:33:01.01 ---      -    -    -    -    *** profile 10
11:34:18.37 ---      -    -    -    -    *** cloud top 4700 ft
11:35:23.35 ---      -    -    -    -    *** reverse p
11:35:26.35 SWS  -6.0 -    -    -    -    Telescope sent to 174.000
11:35:27.25 SWS      -    -    -    -    Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:35:28.06 SWS 171.7 -    -    -    -    Telescope stopped.
11:35:29.88 LSH      -    -    -    -    Dark measurement started.
11:35:29.92 USH      -    -    -    -    Dark measurement started.
11:35:29.95 SWS      -    -    -    -    Dark measurement started.
11:35:31.05 USH      -    -    -    -    Manual scene recording started.
11:35:31.26 SWS      -    -    -    -    Manual scene recording started.
11:35:31.44 LSH      -    -    -    -    Manual scene recording started.
11:35:49.93 ---      -    -    -    -    *** profile 11 descending to 50 ft
11:36:22.70 ---      -    -    -    -    *** cloud top
11:38:19.63 ---      -    -    -    -    *** cloud base
11:40:36.61 ---      -    -    -    -    *** cb at 2900 ft
11:40:54.35 ---      -    -    -    -    *** descen to 50 ft
11:41:16.00 ---      -    -    -    -    *** will change sws to zenith at 50 ft

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11:42:12.24 SWS 174.0 - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
11:42:13.97 SWS -5.8 - - - Telescope stopped.
11:42:49.84 --- - - - *** profile climb to 2500 ft for below cloud
run profile 12
11:44:48.17 --- - - - *** run
11:45:02.46 --- - - - *** run 4.1
11:56:08.97 --- - - - *** end of run start of profile, cloud is
getting thicker and cloud base is dropping significantly
11:56:25.04 --- - - - *** profile 13
11:57:25.68 --- - - - *** run 4.2 3900 ft in cloud
11:58:30.13 --- - - - *** 3700 ft
11:59:33.09 SWS -6.0 - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
11:59:34.83 SWS 173.9 - - - Telescope stopped.
11:59:36.31 USH - - - Dark measurement started.
11:59:36.35 LSH - - - Dark measurement started.
11:59:36.39 SWS - - - Dark measurement started.
11:59:37.32 USH - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:59:37.73 SWS - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:59:38.04 LSH - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:59:56.82 SWS - - - Dark measurement started.
11:59:56.85 USH - - - Dark measurement started.
11:59:56.91 LSH - - - Dark measurement started.
11:59:57.87 SWS - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:59:58.05 USH - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:59:58.21 SWS - - - Dark measurement started.
11:59:58.73 LSH - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:59:59.36 SWS - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:01:10.41 SWS 174.0 - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
12:01:12.18 SWS -5.9 - - - Telescope stopped.
12:07:07.06 --- - - - *** 15 deg
12:07:16.59 --- - - - *** end pof run
12:07:28.31 --- - - - *** profile climb
12:08:08.00 --- - - - *** cloud top
12:08:15.41 --- - - - *** 4600 ft\
12:08:28.11 LSH - - - Dark measurement started.
12:08:28.14 SWS - - - Dark measurement started.
12:08:28.16 USH - - - Dark measurement started.
12:08:29.32 SWS - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:08:29.51 USH - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:08:29.63 LSH - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:09:16.52 --- - - - *** descending
12:09:22.46 USH - - - Idling
12:09:22.50 LSH - - - Idling
12:09:22.53 SWS - - - Idling
12:09:28.99 SWS -6.0 - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
12:09:30.63 SWS - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:09:30.63 LSH - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:09:30.65 USH - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:09:30.77 SWS 173.7 - - - Telescope stopped.
12:10:26.23 --- - - - *** cloud top
12:11:49.18 --- - - - *** cloud base
12:12:10.94 --- - - - *** out of cloud niow
12:13:56.81 --- - - - *** changing to zenith at 50 ft
12:16:16.57 SWS 174.0 - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
12:16:18.36 SWS -5.8 - - - Telescope stopped.
12:16:25.91 --- - - - *** run
12:16:30.07 --- - - - *** at 100 ft
12:16:50.48 --- - - - *** run 5.1
12:19:20.46 LSH - - - Idling
12:19:20.51 SWS - - - Idling
12:19:20.54 USH - - - Idling
12:19:22.25 SWS -6.0 - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
12:19:24.04 SWS 174.0 - - - Telescope stopped.
12:19:24.62 USH - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:19:24.62 LSH - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:19:24.64 SWS - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:19:27.02 LSH - - - Dark measurement started.
12:19:27.09 USH - - - Dark measurement started.
12:19:27.11 SWS - - - Dark measurement started.
```



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12:45:40.99 LSH - - - - Idling
12:45:41.55 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:45:41.55 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:45:41.57 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:45:46.00 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:45:46.07 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:45:46.11 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:45:46.98 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:45:47.40 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:45:47.70 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:47:51.62 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:47:51.63 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:47:51.67 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:47:52.63 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:47:53.06 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:47:53.41 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:48:18.67 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:48:18.70 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:48:18.74 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:48:19.88 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:48:20.14 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:48:20.32 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:48:37.57 --- - - - - *** 15 deg
12:50:40.40 --- - - - - *** end of run
12:50:52.93 --- - - - - *** profile climb to 10000 ft p18
12:51:03.00 LSH - - - - Idling
12:51:03.03 USH - - - - Idling
12:51:03.11 SWS - - - - Idling
12:51:03.19 SWS - - - - Idling
12:51:06.05 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:51:06.06 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:51:06.07 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:51:37.21 --- - - - - *** cloud top
12:51:37.28 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:51:37.29 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:51:37.35 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:51:37.98 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:51:38.48 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:51:38.78 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:51:39.00 SWS - - - - Idling
12:51:42.27 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:51:46.69 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:51:46.72 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:51:46.79 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:51:47.65 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:51:47.85 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:51:48.59 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:55:03.78 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:55:03.82 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:55:03.94 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:55:04.78 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:55:05.20 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:55:05.48 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:55:07.58 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:55:08.57 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:55:09.44 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:55:10.47 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:55:14.18 SWS - - - 30 - VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 30ms.
12:55:14.19 SWS - - - 30 - NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 30ms.
12:55:16.21 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:55:16.96 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:55:18.64 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:55:19.41 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:55:21.18 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:55:22.02 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:56:43.05 --- - - - - *** reversing climb
12:56:52.74 --- - - - - *** descending
12:56:57.95 --- - - - - *** profile 19
12:57:03.19 SWS 174.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000

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12:57:04.98 SWS -5.9 - - - Telescope stopped.
12:57:07.97 SWS - - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:57:08.03 LSH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:57:08.07 USH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:57:08.77 SWS - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:57:09.49 USH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:57:09.79 LSH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:03:12.76 --- - - - - - *** run at 4700 ft
13:03:49.35 SWS -6.0 - - - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
13:03:51.16 SWS 174.0 - - - - - Telescope stopped.
13:04:03.63 --- - - - - - *** skimming cloud top
13:04:38.24 --- - - - - - *** for turbulence measurements
13:05:36.30 SWS - - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:05:36.35 USH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:05:36.46 LSH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:05:37.09 SWS - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:05:37.55 USH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:05:38.23 LSH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:08:30.85 SWS - - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:08:31.64 SWS - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:08:32.23 SWS 174.0 - - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
13:08:34.03 SWS -5.9 - - - - - Telescope stopped.
13:08:34.60 SWS - - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:08:35.44 SWS - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:08:36.28 SWS - - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:08:36.34 LSH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:08:36.43 USH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:08:37.09 SWS - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:08:37.67 USH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:08:38.08 LSH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:09:55.63 USH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:09:55.70 LSH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:09:55.73 SWS - - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:09:56.62 USH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:09:56.90 SWS - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:09:57.32 LSH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:11:54.14 SWS -6.0 - - - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
13:11:55.92 SWS 174.0 - - - - - Telescope stopped.
13:11:58.22 LSH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:11:58.26 USH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:11:58.35 SWS - - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:11:59.44 SWS - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:11:59.48 USH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:11:59.77 LSH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:13:09.45 --- - - - - - *** end of run, descending for an in cloud leg
13:13:41.86 --- - - - - - *** profile 20
13:13:51.14 --- - - - - - *** run
13:13:57.44 --- - - - - - *** at 4200 ft
13:14:08.06 --- - - - - - *** run 6.2
13:14:12.58 LSH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:14:12.63 SWS - - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:14:12.66 USH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:14:13.56 SWS - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:14:13.98 USH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:14:14.15 LSH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:17:01.30 USH - - - - - Idling
13:17:01.34 SWS - - - - - Idling
13:17:01.37 LSH - - - - - Idling
13:17:01.46 LSH - - - - - Idling
13:17:03.65 SWS 174.0 - - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
13:17:05.44 SWS -5.9 - - - - - Telescope stopped.
13:17:05.60 SWS - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:17:05.61 LSH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:17:05.62 USH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:18:16.12 --- - - - - - *** 15 deg
13:19:34.95 LSH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:19:34.98 USH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:19:35.04 SWS - - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:19:35.62 SWS - - - - - Dark measurement started.

14:45:42.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:45:43.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:48:22.69	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:48:24.52	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:48:27.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:48:27.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:48:27.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:48:28.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:48:28.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:48:29.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:48:35.49	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
14:48:43.52	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of profile descent
14:48:49.31	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:48:51.12	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:48:52.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:48:52.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:48:52.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:48:53.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:48:53.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:48:54.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:49:04.63	---	-	-	-	-	*** below cloud
14:49:21.75	---	-	-	-	-	*** run
14:49:31.80	---	-	-	-	-	*** below cloud
14:52:33.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:52:33.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:52:33.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:52:36.48	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:52:38.28	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:52:39.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:52:39.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:52:39.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:52:41.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:52:41.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:52:41.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:52:42.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:52:42.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:52:43.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:52:43.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:52:50.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:53:20.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:53:20.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:53:20.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:53:22.32	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:53:24.14	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:53:24.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:53:24.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:53:24.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:53:26.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:53:26.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:53:26.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:53:27.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:53:27.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:53:27.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:53:28.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:53:29.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:53:29.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:53:29.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:53:30.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:53:30.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:53:30.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:53:31.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:55:50.85	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
14:56:40.56	---	-	-	-	-	*** descending to 2500 ft to avoid cloud base
14:56:49.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:56:49.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:56:49.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:56:50.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:56:50.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:56:51.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

14:59:49.48	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
14:59:55.38	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile descent
15:01:39.36	---	-	-	-	-	*** clear skies
15:02:52.61	---	-	-	-	-	*** 50 ft
15:03:01.30	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile climb to 5000 ft
15:03:09.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:03:09.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:03:09.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:03:10.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:03:10.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:03:11.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:03:11.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:03:13.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:04:41.64	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
15:05:57.00	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud
15:06:09.37	---	-	-	-	-	*** passed through scattere cloud
15:06:18.90	---	-	-	-	-	*** very patchy cloud below
15:06:31.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:06:31.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:06:31.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:06:32.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:06:32.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:06:32.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:19:30.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:26:04.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:26:05.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:26:05.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:26:06.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:26:06.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:26:06.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:26:09.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:26:09.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:26:09.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:26:09.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:26:10.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:26:10.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:26:11.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:26:16.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:26:16.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:26:16.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:26:16.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:26:17.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:26:18.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:26:18.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:26:42.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:26:42.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:26:43.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:26:43.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:26:44.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:26:44.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B417:

Log	Reason
Instrument Status	may not be correct – Flight Manager asked to check
De-brief	Sortie De-brief yet to be created by
Cloud Physics Processing	No cloud physics processing logs are expected for VOCALS flights
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
PSAP log	No log as PSAP pump/filter info included on Flight Summary page
Dry Neph	Operator does not create a log sheet
2D-S / CAPS	2D-S / CAPS operator does not create a log sheet
AMS log	AMS operator does not create a log sheet
VACC	Operator does not create a log sheet

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	16 Sep 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

Digital video recordings in avi format:

faam-video-dfc_faam_20081109_r0_b417_095353_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20081109_r0_b417_105353_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20081109_r0_b417_115353_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20081109_r0_b417_125353_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20081109_r0_b417_135353_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20081109_r0_b417_145353_1hz.avi

faam-video-rfc_faam_20081109_r0_b417_095345_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20081109_r0_b417_105345_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20081109_r0_b417_115345_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20081109_r0_b417_125345_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20081109_r0_b417_135345_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20081109_r0_b417_145345_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20081109_r0_b417_095339_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20081109_r0_b417_105339_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20081109_r0_b417_115339_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20081109_r0_b417_125339_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20081109_r0_b417_135339_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20081109_r0_b417_145339_1hz.avi

faam-video-ufc_faam_20081109_r0_b417_095349_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20081109_r0_b417_105349_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20081109_r0_b417_115349_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20081109_r0_b417_125349_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20081109_r0_b417_135349_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20081109_r0_b417_145349_1hz.avi

No Digital8 video recordings were made on this flight.